

**First certain record of *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
(Hymenoptera: Formicidae) and three ant species new
to the Republic of Macedonia**

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ABSTRACT. First certain record of *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) and three ant species new to the Republic of Macedonia.

Myrmica sabuleti MEINERT, *Stenamma debile* (FÖRSTER) and *Stenamma striatum* EMERY are recorded from Republic of Macedonia for the first time. First certain record of *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER) in the Republic of Macedonia is given. The current list of ants of this country comprises 103 species.

KEY WORDS: ants, Republic of Macedonia, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

Ants of the Republic of Macedonia are poorly known. Recently, BRAČKO *et al.* (2014) published a critical list of 99 species known from this country. They discussed also historical data of 8 species with doubtful occurrence in this country. Their presence in Macedonia was questionable due to recent taxonomic and biogeographic revisions of some Mediterranean ants. By courtesy of Dr. Paweł Jałoszyński (University of Wrocław, Poland) we had an occasion to study a small collection of ants collected by him in Macedonia in 2011. In this material we found three species not recorded previously from this country and one species which occurrence required confirmation.

Photos were taken using a Nikon SMZ 1500 stereomicroscope, Nikon D5200 photo camera and Helicon Focus software. Examined specimens are housed in P. Jałoszyński collection, University of Wrocław, Poland.

LIST OF SPECIES

***Myrmica sabuleti* MEINERT, 1861**

1 worker: Bukovik Mts., vill. Pečkovo env., 880 m, 41°46.617 N / 20°50.395 E, 19 VI 2011, leg. P. Jałoszyński.

One of the commonest European members of the genus *Myrmica*, known also from the most of Balkan countries (BOROWIEC 2014). New to the Republic of Macedonia.

***Stenamma debile* (FÖRSTER, 1850) (Fig. 1)**

1 gyne: Bukovik Mts., vill. Pečkovo env., 880 m, 41°46.617 N / 20°50.395 E, 19 VI 2011, leg. P. Jałoszyński.

Fig. 1. *Stenammina debile* (FÖRSTER), gyne (scale bar = 1 mm) (photo L. Borowiec).

Ryc. 1. *Stenammina debile* (FÖRSTER), królowa (skala = 1 mm) (fot. L. Borowiec).

Fig. 2. *Stenammina striatulum* EMERY, gyne (scale bar = 1 mm) (photo L. Borowiec).

Ryc. 2. *Stenammina striatulum* EMERY, królowa (skala = 1 mm) (fot. L. Borowiec).

European species often misidentified with *S. westwoodi* WESTWOOD, in Balkan area known from Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Montenegro and Serbia (BOROWIEC 2014). New to the Republic of Macedonia.

***Stenamamma striatulum* EMERY, 1895 (Fig. 2)**

1 gyne: Struga region, vill. Modrič env., 666 m, 41°22.069 N / 20°35.284 E, 18 VII 2011, leg. P. Jałoszyński.

Mediterranean species with northern border of distribution in Slovenia and Switzerland. In Balkan area known from Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece and Serbia (BOROWIEC 2014). New to the Republic of Macedonia.

***Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)**

1 worker: Bukovik Mts., vill. Pečkovo env., 880 m, 41°46.617 N / 20°50.395 E, 19 VI 2011, leg. P. Jałoszyński.

This is widely spread species known from the whole Europe and Caucasian countries (BOROWIEC 2014). Although it was recorded three times from the Republic in Macedonia (DOFLEIN 1920, SANTSCI 1926, PETROV 1994) these records need confirmation. Recent revisions of the subgenus *Lasius* s. str. divided former taxon *Lasius alienus* into several distinct taxa (SEIFERT 1992, SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI 2016). Therefore, records mentioned by the listed authors could refer to at least one of the four species from the *L. alienus* complex, i.e. *L. alienus* (FÖRSTER), *L. paralienus* SEIFERT, *L. psammophilus* SEIFERT and *L. bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI. So far, only *L. paralienus* was confirmed for the country (BRAČKO *et al.* 2014). Our data of *L. alienus* is the first certain record for the Republic of Macedonia.

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STRESZCZENIE

Pierwsze pewne stwierdzenie *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) i trzy gatunki mrówek nowe dla Republiki Macedonii

Myrmica sabuleti MEINERT, *Stenamma debile* (FÖRSTER) i *Stenamma striatulum* EMERY zostały wykazane po raz pierwszy z Republiki Macedonii. Podano też pierwsze pewne stwierdzenie *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER) dla tego kraju. Tym samym lista gatunków mrówek znanych z Republiki Macedonii wzrosła do 103.

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